

Unveiling the potential of ultra-thin perovskite-silicon tandem photovoltaics boosted with photonic management

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Abstract. The merging of thin-film photovoltaic (PV) technologies with tandem architectures, such as perovskite-on-silicon double-junction solar cells, offers avenues to expand solar electricity. Their combination of flexibility, affordability, low weight, and high efficiency enables applications ranging from portable electronics to building-integrated and vehicle-integrated PV, or solar-powered space systems. Nevertheless, the efficiency of perovskite-on-silicon tandem PV is often constrained by suboptimal optical management, particularly in ultra-thin designs where light trapping (LT) and current/voltage matching are critical. Here, we develop an optoelectronic framework to optimize 2- and 4-terminal perovskite-silicon tandem cells, featuring 1 μm -thick crystalline silicon absorbers with front-integrated photonic structures. To maximize power conversion efficiency (PCE), both the LT geometry and perovskite thickness were systematically optimized. In addition, indium tin oxide (ITO)-based and optically engineered interlayers are shown to exhibit similar optical performance, reinforcing ITO as a choice for 2-terminal tandems. The ultra-thin photonic-enhanced 2-terminal tandem achieves a PCE of 23.8%, corresponding to a 21.8% relative improvement over its planar counterpart, whereas the 4-terminal configuration reached a combined efficiency of 26.7%, primarily from LT-improved silicon photocurrent. These findings highlight the role of opto-electronically optimized light-management solutions in unlocking the potential of ultra-thin tandem solar cells for flexible, high-efficiency, and energy harvesting, paving the way for next-generation photovoltaics.

Keywords: perovskite-silicon tandem photovoltaics; photonics; light management; thin-film solar cells; opto-electronic modelling; smart-search optimization.

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1 Introduction

Silicon solar cell technology has nearly reached its practical efficiency limit, with the present record at about 27%¹ power conversion efficiency (PCE), nearing the theoretical limits for this type of single-junction cells.² Although crystalline silicon-based photovoltaics (PV) remains the market-dominant solar electricity technology,³ owing to its cost-effectiveness and durability,^{4,5} the need for further PCE improvements is prompting the development of tandem architectures as a strategy to surpass the efficiency ceiling of single-junction silicon PV.

Tandem (multijunction) architectures can solve the spectral limitations of single junctions by stacking materials with different bandgaps, allowing for better absorption of different parts of the solar spectrum while also reducing thermalization losses induced by high-energy photons.⁶ Notable examples include III-V semiconductor multijunction devices,⁷⁻⁹ perovskite-on-silicon,^{1,10,11} perovskite-copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS),^{12,13} perovskite-organic,¹⁴ and all-perovskite tandems.^{9,15} Among the various materials explored for tandem integration, perovskites have been the focus of extensive research^{16,17} owing to their tunable bandgaps,¹⁸ low-cost solution processing,¹⁹ large charge-carrier diffusion lengths,²⁰ and compatibility with thinner and flexible device architectures.²¹ Paired with

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the reliability and scalability of silicon, perovskite-silicon tandems offer a compelling prospect, driving a growing interest.²²

In perovskite-on-silicon tandem architectures, the perovskite layer, ideally with a bandgap around 1.75 eV,^{23,24} captures high-energy photons in the UV and visible wavelength range, while the silicon layer (bandgap of 1.12 eV) absorbs the transmitted lower-energy photons in the near-infrared. Moreover, perovskite solar cells (PSCs) can also achieve high open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) values.^{2,25} This resulted in efficiencies of perovskite-on-silicon tandems up to 34.6%,¹ exceeding the highest-recorded efficiency of single-junction crystalline-Si (c-Si) cells (over 27%⁵) and single-junction PSCs (27%⁹), and approaching the theoretical maximum efficiency of ~44% for perovskite-silicon tandem solar cells.²⁶

There can be three main tandem configurations for the subcells' contacts, each with different limitations in terms of practical implementations. Namely, 2-terminal (2T), 3-terminal (3T), and 4-terminal (4T) configurations, where 2T and 4T are the most commonly employed²⁷ and the architectures focused on in this work. Notably, the lower device (processing) complexity of the 2T configuration has made it the preferred choice in the PV community thus far. Nonetheless, the 4T configuration offers added degrees of freedom for the fabrication of the subcells, such as the mechanical stacking of two independently produced solar cells, separated by an interlayer acting as an electrical decoupler. Besides the potential processing advantages, the 4T subcells can operate independently at their maximum power points while remaining optically coupled, unlike the 2T configuration.

According to Werner et al.,²⁸ among the first successful perovskite ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Pb}_3\text{I}$)-silicon 4T devices were those developed by Bailie et al.¹⁰ and Löper et al.,²⁹ achieving combined efficiencies of 17.0% and 13.4%, respectively. Both groups attributed their reduced efficiencies, compared with theoretical values, to optical losses³⁰⁻³³ (i.e., parasitic absorption and reflection losses) and suboptimal material selection,³⁴⁻³⁸ as well as individual cell inefficiency,^{1,39} which have been the focus of extensive research. The current highest experimentally verified efficiency for a 4T perovskite-silicon tandem solar cell is 33.1%.⁴⁰

In the 2T configuration, the perovskite top cell is directly deposited on the silicon bottom cell, and the two are electrically connected in series through an interlayer or recombination layer.⁴¹ One of the first functional perovskite ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$)-silicon 2T devices was reported by Mailoa et al.,¹¹ achieving a PCE of 13.7%, where the main efficiency-limiting factors were also attributed to parasitic absorption, reflection losses, material selection, and individual cell efficiencies. To date, the most efficient 2T perovskite-silicon tandem sits at 34.6% PCE.⁹ This design is more cost-effective than the 4T configuration, as it requires fewer contact layers. However, although both subcells are in series, their currents must be matched for optimal performance. In addition, the interlayer must be highly transparent to maximize light transmission to the bottom cell but also ensure efficient recombination of the majority carriers, or carrier tunneling, at the interface between the two subcells.⁴¹ Transparent conductive oxides, such as indium tin oxide (ITO),⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ are typically used as interlayer materials due to their favorable physical properties^{45,46} and stability.⁴⁷

Although such efficiency advances mark significant progress, this class of tandem solar cells has typically relied on conventional thick silicon wafers (hundreds of micrometers)^{10,11,29,30,35,40,42} to maintain sufficient light absorption and capitalize on the industrially matured wafer technology. This large thickness limits the

devices' applicability in curved or bendable platforms, for instance, to power flexible electronics or other consumer-oriented systems, as well as in weight-sensitive scenarios such as aerospace technologies.⁴⁸ In addition, thinner perovskite and silicon layers benefit from reduced radiation damage,^{49,50} with perovskites also exhibiting self-healing properties in space-like conditions.^{51,52} Having the aforementioned goals in sight, thinner monolithic perovskite-silicon tandem implementations have been researched, still based in textured crystalline silicon wafers, including bottom cells with 70 μm silicon achieving 33% PCE (19 mA/cm^2 per subcell),⁵³ 30 μm reaching 24% PCE (17 mA/cm^2),⁵⁴ and 60 μm with 27% PCE (17.7 mA/cm^2),⁵⁵ supporting the trend towards further reductions in silicon thickness to decrease material usage and device weight while aiming to increase power density.

To address this, there has been a growing research interest in thin-film cells optically-enhanced with light management strategies,^{4,34,42,56,57} including light trapping (LT) structures,^{30,33,58-68} to reduce material usage (thickness) while ensuring high efficiency. For instance, to improve silicon-based devices, optical modeling has shown that honeycomb structures, composed of wavelength-sized TiO_2 semi-spherical domes, added atop a 1.5 μm thick silicon cell, can lead to a ~50% increase in the generated photocurrent.⁶⁵ Similarly, arrays of TiO_2 void-like semi-spheroids were predicted to increase PCE by 50% in a similar cell, achieving overall better performance than domes.⁶³ Experimentally, such void-like periodic micro-structures were tested in thin amorphous-silicon and crystalline silicon solar cells, demonstrating increases in efficiency above 20%^{62,64} and 30%,⁶¹ respectively. In these cases,^{61,62,64} the photonic structures were fabricated using colloidal lithography, in which ordered monolayers of colloidal spheres act as templates, followed by dry-etching steps that enable controlled tuning of the void diameter and inter-void spacing. Nevertheless, other nanoscale lithography methods have demonstrated promising applications for PV nano/micro-structuring.^{48,69}

For perovskite-based devices, when this type of front-located nanophotonic structure were designed for application onto thin (250 nm) perovskite layer cells, the void and dome periodic textures were shown to increase the photocurrent by 27% and 21%, respectively.⁶⁷ For perovskite-silicon tandems, incorporating inverted-pyramid texturing (300 nm perovskite over an infinitely thick Si bottom cell), combined optical simulations with analytical electrical modelling predicted PCEs of 31.9% for a 2T and 32.0% for a 4T configuration.⁶⁸ Experimental results have corroborated LT-driven efficiency increases, contributing to a PCE of 29.8% in perovskite-silicon tandem cells.⁶⁶ Moreover, IZO and TiO_2 void-like micro-structuring in amorphous silicon thin-film cells led to increases in photocurrent above 18%,^{62,64} and a 30% efficiency gain with TiO_2 nanostructures in crystalline silicon cells.⁶¹

In this light, the present work reports a complete optoelectronic optimization of thin (<3 μm), perovskite-on-silicon tandem solar cells with minimum absorber thicknesses and endowed with state-of-the-art front photonic structures, in view of demonstrating a cost-effective PV approach with high mechanical flexibility plus power density. Namely, the study presents optimized tandem architectures, including the design of the photonic structures, considering an ultra-thin silicon subcell having a fixed 1 μm silicon layer thickness, coupled to a 1.75 eV bandgap perovskite (MAPbI_2Br)^{10,70} top cell with variable perovskite layer thickness (100–700 nm), enhanced by honeycomb

LT front structures composed of semi-spheroidal voids. The optimized designs resulted in PCEs of 23.8% and 26.7% for 2T and 4T, respectively, representing increases of 21.8% and 18.0% over their planar counterparts. In addition, a comparative optical assessment of interlayer materials revealed that ITO performs on par with an ideal lossless interlayer in 2T tandems. Beyond these device results, this work introduces a Python-based workflow that couples 3D finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) optical generation with finite element method (FEM) drift diffusion device (electrical) modeling, and embeds both within a smart-search loop to optimize the photonic-enhanced perovskite-silicon tandem efficiency. This integration, which, to the best of our knowledge, has not yet been reported, has generalized applicability in the field of multijunction PV for the design of different sets of PV materials and layer architectures.

2 Layout and Methods

The tandem architecture considered in the present work is sketched in Fig. 1. The top perovskite subcell consists of the following layers (from top to bottom): ITO electrode, 30 nm titanium dioxide (TiO_2) electron transport layer (ETL), MAPbI_2Br ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_2\text{Br}$) perovskite absorber, and 20 nm

nickel oxide (NiO_x) hole transport layer (HTL). The bottom subcell featured a silicon heterojunction (SHJ) architecture composed of a 1 μm crystalline silicon (c-Si) slab sandwiched between four amorphous silicon (a-Si) layers for passivation and charge transport. The top layers included a 10 nm n-doped a-Si layer (a-Si(n)) and a 10 nm intrinsic a-Si passivating layer (a-Si(i)). Similarly, a 10 nm intrinsic a-Si passivating layer followed by a 10 nm p-doped a-Si layer (a-Si(p)) are placed beneath the c-Si absorber. Finally, a 60 nm aluminum doped zinc oxide (AZO) layer and a 100 nm silver (Ag) electrode were used as the back contact. Between the two subcells, two different interconnection layouts were tested, depicted on the right of Fig. 1:

- In the 2T configuration, the subcells were connected in series with a recombination layer between them. The recombination layer considered here is either ITO or an optically lossless dielectric material with a spectrally-constant real refractive index optimized for the tandem stack (referred to as “lossless interlayer”). In this configuration, electrons generated in the perovskite subcell are collected by the top ITO electrode, while holes from the silicon subcell reach the Ag rear electrode. The remainder of the charge carriers recombine at the interlayer.⁴¹

- In the 4T layout, two ITO layers, separated by a similar lossless interlayer, function as intermediate electrodes, allowing

Fig. 1 Schematic of a perovskite-on-silicon tandem solar cell with integrated LT structures (left), showing the material layers and interlayer configurations (right) for 2-terminal (top) and 4-terminal (bottom) architectures. The LT design incorporates a hexagonal array of semi-spheroidal voids integrated in the front contact layers, with tunable geometrical parameters such as radius (R), height (R_z), and pitch to enhance optical scattering and, consequently, absorption in the perovskite and silicon layers. Additional tunable parameters include the layer thicknesses of the front ITO, perovskite, interlayer (either ITO or a lossless material with a constant real refractive index), and the ITO contacts in the 4T case. In the 2T configuration, the subcells are connected in series, requiring matched photocurrents for optimal performance. In the 4T configuration, each subcell can operate independently. When considering a parallel connection between the perovskite and silicon bottom cells, the cell's V_{OC} is limited by the lower voltage subcell, which constrains the achievable efficiency. Thus, in this work, a halved-Si connection is explored. In this arrangement, the bottom silicon cell is divided into two halves, each with half the PSC area, which are then connected in series. This halved-Si tandem is placed in parallel with the full-area perovskite subcell.

independent extraction from each subcell. In this case, the perovskite-generated holes are extracted at the rear ITO contact, and the silicon-generated electrons are collected at the adjacent ITO layer. Owing to the fact that the V_{OC} of the silicon subcell is close to half of the perovskite subcell V_{OC} , previous contributions³⁴ explored a halved-Si connection: two equal-area silicon bottom subcells, each covering half the area of the perovskite subcell, are connected in series, and this series connection is operated in parallel with the full-area perovskite subcell. The series connection doubles the silicon branch V_{OC} , mitigating voltage mismatch with the perovskite, whereas the parallel connection maintains overall current output. The two silicon halves are placed directly beneath the perovskite footprint to preserve optical coupling, where the main trade-off is the added interconnect complexity.

Beyond their favorable band alignment, the listed transport materials were selected because they are fabrication-standard and widely adopted (see Fig. S1 in the [Supplementary Material](#)), ensuring efficient charge extraction and reducing the tandem's series resistance. The efficient distribution of energy between the two active semiconductors, however, is dictated by their bandgap: the perovskite, with its larger bandgap, absorbs most of the incident light up to its cut-off wavelength ($\lambda = 709$ nm), while the narrower-bandgap silicon subcell captures lower-energy photons, enhancing overall light utilization in the tandem.

To mainly counterbalance the thinness of the silicon layer, light absorption was enhanced by incorporating an LT structure in the form of a honeycomb array of semi-spheroidal voids at the top of the tandem. These voids act as periodic scattering centers that increase the optical path length within the device by redirecting and scattering incoming light at oblique angles, thereby enhancing photon absorption in both subcells. This is particularly important in the silicon layer, where absorption is otherwise limited due to its reduced 1 μm thickness. The choice of a 1 μm silicon thickness was motivated by its position at the onset of the Lambertian LT photocurrent plateau,⁷¹ allowing for high absorption (nearing that of silicon wafers) when efficient LT is implemented, while minimizing material usage and enabling film flexibility. The employed architectures and materials are illustrated in Fig. 1, where the ETL of the top subcell (TiO_2) overcoated with the top electrode (ITO) constitutes the photonic structured layers, similarly to the LT implementation employed in previous studies.^{65,67}

The solar cells were numerically modeled using ANSYS Lumerical software, employing the FDTD solver for the optical simulation and the FEM-based CHARGE solver for the electrical description. The coupling of these solvers was enabled through an in-house Python workflow utilizing the Lumerical API, which is openly available in a GitHub repository.⁷² This integration allows the full optoelectronic study and optimization of solar cells with arbitrary architecture. To optimize the tandem architecture, a particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm was implemented,^{72,73} leveraging this FDTD/CHARGE interoperability as illustrated in Fig. 2.

2.1 Optical and Electrical Modelling

The optical response was computed with FDTD simulations, which solves Maxwell's equations by discretizing time and space, allowing for detailed tracking of electromagnetic wave propagation, absorption, and scattering in diverse materials. The main output of the FDTD simulations is the spectral solar generation rate $g(x, y, z, \lambda)$, obtained from the absorption per

unit volume $P_{\text{abs}}(x, y, z, \lambda)$ normalized by the photon energy $h\nu$, representing the photon-to-carrier conversion, where λ describes the wavelength, h describes the Planck's constant, and ν describes the photon frequency. This spectral generation is then integrated over the solar irradiance spectrum (AM1.5), yielding the solar generation rate $G(x, y, z)$, which is calculated independently for both the perovskite and silicon layers ($G_{\text{PVK}}, G_{\text{Si}}$). For these optical simulations a unitary internal quantum efficiency is considered, in that each absorbed photon generates an electron-hole pair. Under this assumption, the optical photocurrent density (J_{Ph}) is also derived, following Eq. (1), and is used as a key performance metric, where q and c are the electron elementary charge and speed of light in vacuum, respectively; λ_{min} and λ_{max} are the minimum and maximum wavelengths of the simulation interval: 300–1100 nm, $I_{\text{AM1.5}}(\lambda)$ is the solar irradiance spectrum (AM1.5), and $A(\lambda)$ is the device absorption spectrum.

$$J_{\text{Ph}} = \frac{q}{hc} \int_{\lambda_{\text{min}}}^{\lambda_{\text{max}}} \lambda A(\lambda) I_{\text{AM1.5}}(\lambda) d\lambda. \quad (1)$$

The solar generation rates in the absorbers ($G_{\text{PVK}}, G_{\text{Si}}$) are then exported for further analysis in Ansys Lumerical CHARGE, serving as an input in the continuity equations within the drift-diffusion (DD) methodology. For electrical modelling, the CHARGE module solves the DD equations and obtains, among several results, the final JV curves of both perovskite,^{34,60,74} and silicon^{34,75–77} solar cells. In this study, we extend its use to simulate the electrical performance of perovskite-silicon tandem cells enhanced with photonic schemes. To achieve this, the simulations considered intrinsic properties of the materials, neglecting the contribution of nonintrinsic properties. Specifically, in the perovskite and silicon layers, only intrinsic recombination was considered, whereas the ETLs and HTLs were assumed to be recombination-free. In addition, surface recombination was disregarded, and band bending at the contacts was not accounted for. This approach is similar to that employed by Richter et al.,⁷⁸ used to theoretically establish the practical efficiency limits for c-Si cells.

2.2 Intelligent-Search Optimization

The PSO algorithm is a population-based method that iteratively searches for the best parameter set (in this case, the optimal cell geometry) within a defined parameter space, i.e., respecting the physical constraints of the system. The search domain (indicated in Table S1 in the [Supplementary Material](#)) was defined to ensure meaningful optical and electrical performance variation and efficient cell operation. The distinct behavior of the 2T and 4T solar cell configurations required different figures of merit (FoMs) to evaluate the performance of each subcell:

- The 2T configuration requires maximizing the individual performance of each subcell while also ensuring current matching between them, as the subcells are connected in series. To achieve this, the FoM defined in Eq. (2) considers the lowest of the photocurrents supplied in the perovskite ($J_{\text{Ph,PVK}}$) and silicon ($J_{\text{Ph,Si}}$) subcells. By maximizing the smaller of the two currents, the algorithm incrementally converges to equalize the current densities at the highest possible value. Increasing the current in a subcell tends to decrease the current in the other cell due to absorption trade-offs inherent in the tandem structure. Through iterative adjustments, the system achieves current

Fig. 2 Schematic of the PSO framework used in this work, incorporating ANSYS® Lumerical FDTD for optical modelling and Lumerical CHARGE for the electrical modeling. The optimization begins with the 3D optical modeling. Using FDTD simulations, the absorption spectrum ($A(\lambda)$) in the perovskite and silicon media is determined. For a 2T configuration, the absorption is used to calculate the photocurrent (J_{Ph}) for both active materials. The figure of merit (FoM) in the PSO algorithm is then determined as the minimum of the two photocurrents to ensure current matching. For a 4T configuration, the radiative recombination coefficient (B) is obtained from $A(\lambda)$, and if the front contact is structured, the generation profiles (G_{PVK} , G_{Si}) generated from the optical modeling are planarized following the method developed by Haque et al.⁶⁰ Both B and the generation profiles serve as inputs for the 2D electrical modeling. The electrical modeling yields, among other results, the JV curve for each subcell, from which the respective PCEs are determined and used to compute the FoM in the 4T configuration.

matching, optimizing overall performance, relying exclusively on the optical FDTD simulations, as detailed in Fig. 2.

$$\text{FoM}_{2T} = \min(J_{Ph,PVK}, J_{Ph,Si}). \quad (2)$$

• For the 4T configuration, the cells' interconnections can be performed at the module level to avoid the need for current or voltage matching between the subcells, allowing for more freedom in the power delivery. As such, it is sufficient to optimize the individual performance of each subcell independently. Thus, the FoM in this configuration was defined as Eq. (3), where PCE_{PVK} and PCE_{Si} represent the power conversion efficiencies of the perovskite and silicon subcells, respectively.

$$\text{FoM}_{4T} = \text{PCE}_{PVK} \times \text{PCE}_{Si}. \quad (3)$$

The evaluation of FoM_{4T} relies on the electric simulations in CHARGE to determine the current density-voltage (JV) curves and PCEs. As per Fig. 2, the optical (FDTD computed) G_{PVK}

and G_{Si} , and the absorption spectrum (A_{PVK} , A_{Si}) for each active material are then used as inputs for the electrical simulations. If the architecture is structured, the generation profiles are planarized, enabling 2D electrical simulations, which significantly reduces computational time while maintaining accuracy as verified in previous works.⁶⁰

For the 2T tandem optimization process, only the subcells optical (photocurrent) performance is accounted for in the FoM_{2T} , since the final tandem PCE is directly proportional to the sum of the subcells' voltage at the maximum power point. For simplicity of the analysis, it is assumed that such voltages (i.e., the electrical performances) are unaffected by the tuning of the geometrical parameters (depicted in Fig. 1) optimized in this study.

3 Results and Discussion

Before analyzing the tandem architecture, each subcell was first modeled and examined independently, as described in the following two sub-sections (for additional information, see Secs. S1–S7 in the [Supplementary Material](#)).

3.1 Ultra-Thin Silicon Cells

Richter et al.⁷⁸ established the theoretical efficiency limits for silicon solar cells by considering exclusively intrinsic recombination while incorporating new optical properties for silicon. Their refined model included radiative and Auger recombination, perfect anti-reflection front coatings, perfect rear mirrors, bandgap narrowing, and Lambertian LT. Under these assumptions, a 1 μm silicon cell was predicted to reach $J_{\text{SC}} = 34 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $\text{FF} = 90\%$, $V_{\text{OC}} = 0.83 \text{ V}$, and $\text{PCE} = 25\%$. This framework served as a starting point for our Si-cell electrical modeling, where we exclusively assume intrinsic recombination in the c-Si layer using a material-specific carrier lifetime curve (see Sec. S3 in the [Supplementary Material](#)).

However, unlike Richter et al.'s⁷⁸ treatment, our simulations account for a-Si passivation layers present in the silicon heterojunction (SHJ) architecture. These layers introduce defect and band-tail states that alter carrier recombination dynamics and degrade device performance.⁷⁹ To capture these effects, the developed CHARGE simulations were compared with the analytical tool AFORS-HET,⁸⁰ which explicitly models defect and band-tail states in SHJ technology.

Figure 3(a) shows this comparison. The solid purple curve represents the AFORS-HET JV output, including the a-Si density of states (DOS), whereas the dashed light purple curve corresponds to the idealized defect- and tail-states free case. The solid blue curve shows our CHARGE simulation, where doping concentrations and carrier lifetimes were adjusted to mimic the impact of the a-Si DOS. This approach reproduces the AFORS-HET curve, yielding $J_{\text{SC}} = 16 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $\text{FF} = 77\%$,

$V_{\text{OC}} = 0.73 \text{ V}$, and $\text{PCE} = 8.9\%$. Accordingly, the dashed light blue curve is the DOS-free CHARGE case, which aligns with the corresponding AFORS-HET results. Also importantly, the V_{OC} ($\sim 0.85 \text{ V}$) and FF ($\sim 89\%$) in the idealized case agree with Richter et al.'s model,⁷⁸ confirming consistency across software and methods. The J_{SC} deviation (and consequently in PCE) arises from the architecture-specific generation profile obtained from our optical FDTD simulations, which capture reflection and parasitic absorption losses and exclude Lambertian LT (discussed in Sec. S5 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). Further details on the method used to mimic the a-Si DOS effects are provided in Sec. S6 in the [Supplementary Material](#).

Experimental demonstrations of ultra-thin 1 μm Si-cells are scarce. Among the few reports, Depauw et al.⁸¹ achieved a PCE of 4.1% with a 1 μm thick monocrystalline Si film with a-Si passivating layers, roughly half the simulated PCEs shown in Fig. 3(a). This gap underscores the significant opportunity for further experimental development of ultra-thin c-Si PV technology.

3.2 Wide-Bandgap Perovskite Cells

Perovskites have been the subject of many electrical DD-based simulation analyses,^{34,60,74,82–84} particularly MAPbI_3 ($\sim 1.55 \text{ eV}$ bandgap), whose well-characterized properties provide a benchmark for other MA-based perovskites. In this work, MAPbI_2Br (bandgap $\sim 1.75 \text{ eV}$) was chosen as the top-cell absorber, given its suitability for Si-based tandems. However, unlike MAPbI_3 , MAPbI_2Br remains less characterized for DD modeling, requiring some parameters to be inferred or adapted (Table S3 in the

Fig. 3 (a) JV curve plots and cell PCEs obtained from CHARGE (in blue) and AFORS-HET (in purple) when considering the tail and defect states of the a-Si DOS (solid lines) and when no defects and tail states are considered (dashed lines). The top values display the a-Si n/p doping concentrations taken in each case, illustrating the parameters used to replicate the impact of the a-Si DOS in CHARGE (blue), as well as the corresponding values in AFORS-HET (purple). (b) Radiative recombination coefficient B (right axis) versus perovskite absorber thickness, as determined by Eq. (4) and the FDTD-derived perovskite absorption (B_{FDTD}). The coefficient B (B_{SQ}) can also be determined with a step-like absorption model, as is used in the Shockley–Queisser (SQ) method (purple, dashed). In addition, the plot shows the perovskite subcell V_{OC} , simulated in CHARGE using the B_{FDTD} (blue, solid), comparing it with the V_{OC} calculated using the SQ method (solid black, with FDTD-derived J_{SC} and dark saturation current density J_0 , k_B as Boltzmann constant, and T as 300 K). The value of the SQ V_{OC} limit for a material with a 1.75 eV bandgap is also indicated (gray, horizontal dashed line). The absorption-derived V_{OC} exceeds the SQ limit, which can be attributed to the higher radiative recombination predicted by the SQ formalism, where all photons above the bandgap are assumed to be absorbed.

Supplementary Material). One key input is the radiative recombination coefficient (B), for which MAPbI₂Br data are scarce. As such, B was determined by the detailed balance principles via Eq. (4):

$$\int A(E)\phi_{\text{BB}}(E, 300 \text{ K})dE = LBn_i^2, \quad (4)$$

where $A(E)$ is the absorption profile in the active material in the cell, ϕ_{BB} is the black-body emission spectrum, L is the absorber thickness, and n_i is the intrinsic carrier density (see Sec. S2 in the **Supplementary Material**). By linking B directly to $A(E)$, the model captures how optical interference in thin-films propagates to the electrical domain. This is clarified in Fig. 3(b), where the relation between B and the perovskite thickness is analyzed: B (purple, solid) decreases with increasing film thickness, and the thin-film optical interference propagates from the optical to the electrical domain, producing thickness dependent modulations in V_{OC} (blue, solid) (for other cell performance metrics, see Sec. S2 in the **Supplementary Material**).

Experimental studies on MAPbI₂Br perovskites show $J_{\text{SC}} = 10 - 19 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, $V_{\text{OC}} = 1.01 - 1.05 \text{ V}$, $\text{FF} = 65\% - 73\%$, and $\text{PCE} = 7.9\% - 12.7\%$.⁸⁵⁻⁸⁸ By contrast, as shown in Fig. 3(b) (and Fig. S2 in the **Supplementary Material**), our simulations predict that V_{OC} varies from 1.48 to 1.52 V, FF from 75% to 81%, J_{SC} from 12 to 19 mA/cm², and PCE from 14% to 21%, within

the specified perovskite thickness range. This gap reflects both the idealized assumptions of the model and the non-idealities present in real devices, such as extrinsic recombination losses, nonideal top layers reducing absorption, higher recombination rates associated with material imperfections, below-bandgap absorption, which can lead to increased radiative recombination losses, and imperfect transport layers and contacts, further affecting charge extraction, and reducing V_{OC} and efficiency.

3.3 Optimized Photonic-Enhanced Tandems

Following the optimization procedure described in Sec. 2, Table 1 lists the optimized geometrical parameters of the LT structures indicated in Fig. 1: array pitch, void radius (R), depth (z -radius, R_z), as well as the optimized layer thicknesses of the perovskite, front ITO electrode, intermediate ITO electrodes (in 4T configuration), and interlayer. Two different interlayers are evaluated: an ITO interlayer, whose properties are incorporated in the optical simulations, and an idealized lossless dielectric interlayer, whose real refractive index is treated as an additional optimization variable, also highlighted in Table 1.

The corresponding absorption and JV curves were determined for each optimized architecture [see Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) and Fig. S12 in the **Supplementary Material**], yielding the cell performance metrics summarized in Table S7 in the **Supplementary Material** and the PCE values in Fig. 4(c).

Table 1 Optimized parameters of the tandem solar cell architectures for the 2T and 4T scenarios presented in Fig. 1, with and without (planar) the semi-spheroidal LT structures integrated in the front contact, and with distinct interlayer materials.

		2T		4T	
		Planar	Void	Planar	Void
ITO interlayer					
LT structure	Pitch [units of R]	–	2.00	–	–
	R [nm]	–	454.29	–	–
	R_z [nm]	–	521.19	–	–
Layer thickness	Perovskite [nm]	106.39	161.47	–	–
	Front ITO [nm]	50.00	50.00	–	–
	Interlayer [nm]	20.28	20.00	–	–
Total tandem thickness [nm]		1426.67	2002.66	–	–
Lossless interlayer					
LT structure	Pitch [units of R]	–	1.49	–	1.59
	R [nm]	–	500.00	–	428.60
	R_z [nm]	–	450.00	–	1000.00
Layer thickness	Perovskite [nm]	111.52	200.00	210.00	344.89
	Front ITO [nm]	64.38	80.90	71.00	50.00
	Interlayer [nm]	91.78	250.00	250.00	20.00
	Intermediate ITOs [nm]	–	–	87.00	50.00
Real refractive index of interlayer		3.48	3.00	1.30	4.00
Total tandem thickness [nm]		1517.68	2230.90	1868.00	2714.89

Fig. 4 (a) Left: JV curves for 2T tandems comparing the LT-structured (solid) and planar (dashed) designs. Dark purple lines correspond to the devices with a lossless interlayer, and light purple lines to those with an ITO interlayer. Center: subcell JV curves for the silicon bottom subcell (green) and perovskite top subcell (blue). Right: JV curves for the 4T tandems. The direct parallel-connected version (pink) shows reduced voltage, which is recovered in the halved-Si (dark purple), resulting in a tandem performance similar to the combination of the subcells' PCE. (b) Combined absorption spectrum of the LT-structured 2T tandem solar cell (black, solid) with the ITO interlayer, obtained as the sum of the perovskite and Si subcell absorption spectra, together with the individual subcell spectra. Solid lines correspond to the LT-structured configuration and dashed lines to the planar case. In the perovskite layer (blue), the LT structure reduces absorption below 384 nm (-0.32 mA/cm²) but enhances absorption beyond that wavelength ($+3.70$ mA/cm²).

Fig. 4 (Continued) In the silicon cell, absorption losses below 670 nm (-1.33 mA/cm^2) are outweighed by the improvement in the near-infrared ($+6.33 \text{ mA/cm}^2$). The gray dashed curve outlines the absorption when considering Lambertian LT for a $1 \mu\text{m}$ silicon layer and a 161 nm perovskite layer, setting a theoretical absorption limit. **(c)** Bar plot showing the perovskite, silicon, and tandem (dark purple, light purple, and pink) PCEs. Solid bars are the values of the LT-structured cells; hatched are the planar. Lighter shades indicate devices with an ITO interlayer (“ITO Inter.”). The “Total” 4T curve refers to combined efficiency of each subcell. The dashed gray line highlights the efficiency limit for a 1161 nm silicon cell, according to Richter et al.⁷⁸ **(d)** Heatmap showing the angularly resolved absorption spectra (i.e., absorption as a function of the light impinging angle) in the silicon material for the optimized 2T with an ITO interlayer. The introduction of the light-scattering voids enhances absorption beyond normal incidence, particularly in the 700–1000 nm spectral region. **(e)** Optical analysis of photocurrent (spectrally integrated absorption) contributions, determined with FDTD simulations, for each optimized tandem configuration. In purple, the total absorption; in pink the parasitic absorption and in orange the current losses associated with reflection. The LT-structured configurations (solid bars) show an increase in the useful absorption (see Fig. S12 in the [Supplementary Material](#)), as well as in their parasitic absorption, but a reduction in the reflection losses, relative to their planar counterparts. Note that, despite the additional layers and consequent parasitic absorption in the 4T devices, the tandem useful absorption is larger than in the 2T design due to the lack of current-matching constraints.

Notably, the total thickness of the tandem cells (including the LT structures) is below $3 \mu\text{m}$ for all configurations, which allows for mechanically-bendable devices. Based on a simple analytical multilayer mechanical analysis,⁸⁹ using material-specific critical strain limits, and considering a standard $125 \mu\text{m}$ thick polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrate, all architectures remain bendable to radii above $\sim 5 \text{ mm}$ (see Tables S8–S9 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). With the top ITO electrode as the limiting layer,⁹⁰ this minimum bending radius approximation is consistent with those attained for other thin-film devices with similar thickness.^{90–95} Moreover, the periodic nano-structured LT features are not expected to significantly hinder bendability,^{96,97} with some geometries (as the present hexagonal/honeycomb array) potentially enabling the strengthening of the devices’ flexural robustness.^{96–99}

The structured LT-enhanced geometries are thicker than their planar counterparts due to increased perovskite thickness and void depth. The photonic void features enhance light scattering, improving optical path length and, consequently, absorption, mainly in the $1 \mu\text{m}$ silicon layer. As a result, the perovskite thickness can be increased without compromising current matching (for 2T) or favoring one subcell in detriment of the other (for 4T). In addition, the interlayer thickness is generally greater when composed of the optically lossless dielectric, as the absence of parasitic absorption removes the need to minimize its thickness.

Despite these geometric adjustments, every optimized architecture retains a perovskite layer thickness below 350 nm, which is lower than the common $\sim 500 \text{ nm}$ thickness^{11,40,42,66,100–102} employed in conventional wafer-supported perovskite-on-silicon tandems. Such a low optimum perovskite thickness brings key advantages, not only for improved flexibility but also to mitigate the presence of toxic lead (Pb) in the devices. According to the Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) Directive, the maximum permissible Pb content in electronic devices is 0.1% of the total device weight. To ensure compliance, the Pb content per unit area was calculated based on the geometric configuration of each optimized architecture (Tables S4 and S5 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). The results show that, in all cases, the amount of Pb remains within the allowed limit, with the highest value corresponding to $\sim 80\%$ of the maximum allowed

concentration in the 4T LT-structured architecture. It is worth noting that this estimate does not account for cell encapsulation or substrate, which would further decrease the percentual Pb mass per m^2 . As such, the proposed ultra-thin tandem cells safely comply with environmental regulations and can be employed in terrestrial applications.

Figure 4(c) shows that the introduction of LT structuring in the 2T architecture with lossless interlayer results in a tandem PCE of 23.8%, representing a 21.8% increase relative to the optimized planar configuration. When the interlayer is ITO, the LT structures increase the PCE by 22.6%, also reaching 23.8%. Similarly, for the 4T configuration, the combined subcell PCE reached 26.7%, representing a 17.9% improvement over the planar scenario. While these PCE values are still below the current 2T and 4T records with wafer-supported perovskite-silicon tandems,^{9,40} they are achieved in much thinner devices (by two orders of magnitude), where the efficiency gains are primarily a result of the improved optical design rather than solely absorber thickness. Specifically, the introduction of periodic voids in the high-index TiO_2 ETL causes pronounced scattering of the impinging light, increasing its propagation path length within the device, and thereby absorption at off-normal angles (see Fig. 4(d) and Figs. S13–S14 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). This boosts the generated photocurrent without the need to increase absorber layer thickness. The additional optimization of the thickness of the top cell and intermediate layers serves as a complement to the LT structures, ensuring reduced unwanted reflection and absorption, improving light distribution across the tandem, i.e., enhancing spectral utilization in the active materials (see Fig. S15 in the [Supplementary Material](#) for further details on the impact of optimization).

Figure 4(a)-center and left—show enhanced efficiency, which can be attributed to LT structuring increasing J_{ph} in both absorber layers. This is further detailed in Fig. 4(b) (and Fig. S12 in the [Supplementary Material](#)), which illustrates how the photonic-structured geometry improves spectral utilization in both subcells. Notably, the perovskite layer benefits from LT in the visible range (also partly attributable to its increased thickness), despite some UV losses associated with the increase in the front contact thickness (structured TiO_2 and overcoated ITO), whereas the $1 \mu\text{m}$ silicon sees a boost in the near infrared wavelengths.

As per the efficiency improvements (listed in Table S7 in the [Supplementary Material](#)), in the 2T configuration, both subcells benefit comparably from the introduction of LT. However, in the 4T case, the enhancement is uneven, with the silicon subcell exhibiting a 31.9% J_{SC} gain and the perovskite subcell only a 15.4% enhancement. Because the subcells operate independently in 4T, the perovskite subcell in the planar configuration can absorb more than in the 2T architecture, reaching larger J_{SC} values. As a result, the introduction of the LT voids in the 4T provides limited additional absorption benefit to the perovskite without compromising the performance of the silicon subcell. In addition, in both the planar and LT-structured 2T configurations, the lossless interlayer exhibits negligibly higher J_{SC} compared with the ITO interlayer, resulting in a PCE increase of around

1.2%. That is, when the geometry is optimized, ITO performs just as well as an optically lossless interlayer with an ideal refractive index, regardless of top-layer structuring. This interplay between geometry and FoM is contextualized in Fig. 5(b) in Sec. 3.5, which evaluates how sensitive the device performance is to geometric variations.

For the 4T subcell architectures (depicted on the right of Fig. 1), the LT structured halved-Si 4T configuration exhibits a PCE of 26.8%, which is 34.5% larger than when a standard parallel connection is employed (~17.6%, see Sec. S11.2 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). This relative gain is V_{OC} driven, as the two series-connected halved silicon bottom cells output $2V_{OC,Si} \approx 1.47$ V, thwarting V_{OC} mismatch between the perovskite and silicon subcells [see Fig. 4(a)-right]. It also outperforms

Fig. 5 (a) Distribution of data from the PSO iterations for the example of the LT-structured 2T with an ITO interlayer, showing the impact of geometric deviations from the optimal parameters on the FoM. The shaded region highlights the interval where the parameter deviation is below 10%, and the red dashed line the ΔFoM at 5%. (b) JV curves of the LT-structured tandem devices exhibiting a maximum deviation from FoM within the 10% parameter variation interval for the 2T configuration with an ITO interlayer compared with the JVs of the optimal tandem geometries. The maximum 6% FoM variation yields a ~5% reduction in PCE. (c) For the 2T lossless interlayer (left plot), the 12% variation reduced the PCE by ~13%. Similarly, for the 4T (right plot) configuration with a lossless interlayer, a 7% maximum decrease in FoM leads to a reduction of ~2% in tandem PCE.

the 2T cells and the combined efficiency of the individual cells in the 4T configuration.

3.4 Comparison with Theoretical Limits

Richter et al.⁷⁸ reported that the maximum theoretical PCE of thin single-junction c-Si solar cells with Lambertian LT and absorber thickness in the range of 1161-1344 nm, corresponding to the combined thickness of the Si and perovskite layers in our optimized tandems (see Table 1), is approximately 27% under AM 1.5G illumination [Fig. 4(c) and Fig. S16(a)-left in the [Supplementary Material](#)]. This value is below the 33% SQ limit,¹⁰³ which assumes infinite active layer thickness. [This value denotes the radiative-only SQ limit under AM1.5 with ideal optics. The original 1961 blackbody-based result is ~30% at the (5) silicon bandgap.] In comparison, the simulated tandems achieve PCEs between 23.8% and 26.8%, with the best case (optimized LT-enhanced 4T halved-Si configuration) attaining the limit predicted by Richter et al.⁷⁸ for the same effective thickness (and below the SQ limit by 7% absolute efficiency). The higher PCE in Richter et al.'s⁷⁸ model arises mainly from the J_{SC} reaching nearly 40 mA/cm², compared with a maximum J_{SC} of 29 mA/cm² of our tandems (Fig. S16 in the [Supplementary Material](#)). This difference reflects the power distribution between subcells: tandems leverage the high V_{oc} of the perovskite top subcell but necessarily deliver lower current. In addition, the lower performances observed in the devices designed in this work are attributable to idealized assumptions in the Richter et al.'s⁷⁸ theoretical model, such as the previously mentioned perfectly reflecting rear mirrors, non-reflective front surfaces, lack of parasitic absorption in transport or interfacial layers, and ideal Lambertian LT.¹⁰⁴ By contrast, the simulated tandem designs account for these architecture-specific losses, leading to the efficiency gap and highlighted in Fig. 4(e), where the impact of optical losses is reflected in the J_{ph} . Despite such losses present in realistic implementations, this work demonstrates that ultra-thin perovskite-silicon tandems can reach the idealized single-junction silicon cell efficiency limit with comparable active layer thickness. Similarly, for a single-junction perovskite solar cell with an equivalent absorber thickness of 1161 nm, the SQ limit with Lambertian LT predicts a PCE of 28.2% [see Fig. S16(a)-left in the [Supplementary Material](#)]. Notably, this value is close to the infinite-thickness limit for a 1.75 eV bandgap material, as the high absorption coefficient of the perovskite yields near step-like absorption, making further thickness increases negligible [see Fig. S16(b) in the [Supplementary Material](#)]. Thus, the optimized 4T LT-structured halved-Si tandem lies within a difference of 2% absolute efficiency of both Si and perovskite single-junction limits, despite including realistic optical and electrical losses.

Double-junction SQ limits with Lambertian LT for 2T architectures [Fig. S16(a)-right in the [Supplementary Material](#)] reach ~29% PCE (determined with the methodology in Sec. S10 and discussed in Sec. S11.1 in the [Supplementary Material](#)), which is an increase of 4.2% in absolute efficiency over the simulated curves of equal thickness. Here, the advantage stems from higher V_{OC} rather than J_{SC} . Our simulated 2T tandem achieves J_{sc} values consistent with the SQ case, not because each subcell's absorption spectrum is identical to the limit case [see Fig. 4(b)], but because light distribution allows residual Si absorption above the perovskite bandgap. The PCE discrepancy between the limits and simulated curves is a consequence of the SQ method's

idealized treatment of the subcells' photovoltage, which predicts Si V_{OC} values close to 0.9 V, higher than achievable in practice [see Fig. S7(b) in the [Supplementary Material](#)].

For 4T designs, it is interesting to analyze the illustrative case plotted in Fig. 4(a)-right of the JV (in pink) that would result from a direct parallel connection between the silicon and perovskite subcells with equal area—and compare it with the halved-Si configuration (represented in the bottom-right of Fig. 1). The efficiency gap with the SQ approach is more impactful in the 4T with a parallel-connected configuration (theoretical PCE limit = 28.4%), owing to the establishment of voltage matching between the subcells, which results in a low tandem V_{OC} (0.76 V) in the optimized simulations. In addition, the J_{SC} decrease associated with the optical losses (absent in the SQ model) further extends this difference from the theoretical limit. By contrast, in the theoretical halved-Si 4T configuration (limit PCE = 36.7%), the perovskite subcell limits the tandem V_{OC} , because the perovskite V_{OC} (~1.5 V) is lower than twice the silicon V_{OC} (~1.8 V). Notably, the simulated perovskite V_{OC} is similar to the idealized value used in the limit calculation, which means that, in this case, the difference in performance stems from current, primarily caused by the optical losses inherent to the tandem architecture and detailed in Fig. 4(e).

3.5 Off-Optimum Tolerance Analysis

Quantifying the allowed fabrication deviations in the geometrical parameters is key to defining realistic device architectures. For that, the computed PSO data were analyzed as a function of the weighted deviation from the optimal geometries (Table 1), applying a 10% geometric perturbation across all cases to assess the robustness of LT-enhanced tandems in terms of FoM variation (ΔFoM). For 2T tandems with an ITO interlayer, this translates to less than 5% of ΔFoM [Fig. 5(a), see also Fig. S17 in the [Supplementary Material](#) for the remaining architectures]. By contrast, lossless interlayers are more sensitive, with maximum ΔFoM up to 11% and 7% for the 2T and 4T devices, respectively. The largest PCE loss across all cases corresponds to 13% [Figs. 5(b) and 5(c)]. These findings demonstrate that the LT-enhanced tandems generally incur modest efficiency penalties under realistic fabrication errors. Such tolerance underscores the practical manufacturability of the proposed LT-enhanced ultra-thin tandems and their potential for scalable photovoltaic integration.

4 Conclusion

This study developed a complete optoelectronic framework, implemented with intelligent-search optimization, to tailor and optimize the design of thin tandem devices with front-integrated photonic structuring. The approach, generalizable to any type of multijunction PV, was applied to ultra-thin perovskite-silicon tandems with a 1 μm Si active layer to determine the potential of planar architectures and devices enhanced by state-of-the-art periodic LT structures (composed of a periodic honeycomb array integrated in the cells' front selective contact).

Different types of subcells' electrical connections were evaluated in the tandem architectures. In the 2T configuration, the optimized LT-structured devices reached a PCE of 23.8%, a 21.8% improvement over their planar counterpart, and ~5% in absolute efficiency below the 28.9% idealized theoretical efficiency limit. The 4T configuration yielded a combined

efficiency of 26.7%, 18.0% higher than the planar counterpart and close to the limit for single-junction Si cells with similar absorber thickness. This highlights the effectiveness of photonic structuring and layer optimization in sub-3 μm tandem devices. In addition, interlayer studies showed that ITO recombination layers performed optically on par with ideal lossless interlayers, affirming ITO as a suitable material choice in 2T tandems.

The photonic-boosted ultra-thin tandem design here proposed enables applications in lightweight, mechanically flexible PV systems (potentially capable of ~ 5 mm bending radius) while maintaining high efficiency and performance robustness against geometric variations. Finally, the ultra-thin design mitigates the amount of toxic Pb content in the device, ensuring it remains below the RoHS threshold, supporting integration into next-generation photovoltaics.

Code and Data Availability

All the relevant code used to generate the results is available in https://github.com/perspe/em_methods.

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